

Provisional mechanism for *sudden wilting* of the rice variety Yushin.

unfavorable weather and soil conditions. We describe a provisional mechanism for *sudden wilting* of Yushin in the figure. Further investigations into air space and

oxygen transport ability of rice varieties are under way. They may throw light on varietal differences in tolerance for some known physiological disorders. ❧

When sprayed at the seedling stage, both Bzi and zinc sulfate were ineffective on NC1281 but increased yield in Jaya (see table). The two chemicals significantly increased yield components as well as yield per plant in both varieties when they were sprayed at preflowering and postflowering stages. The effect was greatest when the chemicals were applied at a later stage of growth. Plant growth was found related directly to yield. Sprayed at the preflowering stage, both Bzi and zinc sulfate were more effective in increasing yield in NC1281 than in Jaya; when sprayed at postflowering the two chemicals were equally effective in increasing the yield parameters of both varieties. Higher yield at the later stages might be due to efficient preflowering translocation as shown by the higher grain:straw ratio.

The two chemicals did not increase seed protein content; however, a slight increase in protein content was observed in Jaya sprayed with Bzi at preflowering stage. ❧

Increased productivity in tall and dwarf rice varieties through benzimidazole and zinc sulfate sprays

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We previously reported that spraying Jaya rice with cytokinins and zinc salt ($ZnSO_4$) at a particular developmental stage was effective in increasing yield. In this experiment, the effectiveness of benzimidazole (Bzi) and zinc sulfate as foliar sprays was observed on yield and yield components of the photoperiod-sensitive tall rice variety NC1281 and the photoperiod-insensitive dwarf Jaya. Aqueous solutions (100 $\mu g/ml$) of Bzi and zinc sulfate were sprayed on the rice plant at seedling, preflowering, and postflowering stages. The growth and yield parameters considered were plant height, straw weight, number of panicles, percentage of ripened grains, grain:straw ratio, yield per plant, and protein content of the seeds.

Effect of benzimidazole and zinc on some yield parameters of tall (NC1281) and dwarf (Jaya) rice varieties, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Straw wt (g/plant)	Yield parameters at harvest				
				Panicles (no./plant)	Grain wt (no./plant)	Grain:straw ratio	Ripened grains (%)	Protein content (mg/g)
<i>Seedling stage (48 days old)</i>								
NC1281	Bzi	146.5	74.4	10.2	23.1	0.311	89.4	75.3
	Zn	145.4	63.4	8.8	23.5	0.370	90.6	74.1
Jaya	Bzi	89.0	32.0	10.0	18.3	0.572	72.9	79.0
	Zn	85.8	30.8	13.4	21.5	0.699	65.4	86.6
<i>Preflowering stage (80 days old)</i>								
NC1281	Bzi	152.6	81.8	10.0	27.8	0.340	93.3	74.8
	Zn	146.6	81.0	12.2	28.7	0.353	90.2	80.6
Jaya	Bzi	94.6	48.4	10.8	19.3	0.396	69.8	91.4
	Zn	92.7	42.7	10.0	16.5	0.306	67.9	84.6
<i>Postflowering stage (96 days old)</i>								
NC1281	Bzi	147.0	78.2	11.4	28.4	0.363	91.6	80.6
	Zn	144.8	76.4	14.2	31.4	0.401	89.6	80.6
Jaya	Bzi	94.3	51.0	11.2	20.9	0.410	74.0	85.0
	Zn	90.8	46.0	15.6	23.2	0.504	69.6	85.5
<i>Control</i>								
NC1281		149.6	76.4	10.6	24.0	0.314	91.8	90.7
Jaya		92.2	40.6	10.0	16.2	0.398	70.4	84.6